

AN ALTERNATE SYNTHESIS OF 7-CHLORO-4-(4'-HYDROXY)-ANILINOQUINOLINE

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Synthesis of 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinoline by cyclodehydration of β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -carbethoxyacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide has been described.

The usual procedure for the preparation of 4-aminoquinoline derivatives involves treatment of the requisite 4-chloroquinoline with requisite amines. Thus, camoquin, 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-diethylaminomethyl)-anilinoquinoline, the well-known anti-malarial drug of commerce, was synthesised from 4:7-dichloroquinoline, the preparation of which involved a large number of steps and removal of one 5-chloro isomer from one intermediate step, thereby reducing the yield in one of its process of its manufacture (Kenyon *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1949, 41, 604). The other process which requires the use of ethoxymethylenemalonic ester is rather costly.

Price and Boekelheide (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1246) established a general method by which a 4-substituted aminoquinoline could be directly synthesised by cyclodehydration of β -anilinoacrylamides, followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation according to the following scheme :

Ring-closure always took place involving the *para* position in the case of *meta*-substituted anilines, affording 7-isomeric quinolines only. The reaction takes place smoothly when 'R' in the structure is an aromatic nucleus. But the 4-alkylaminoquinolines in which the alkyl group contained an amino-substituent, failed entirely. Thus,

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the attempts of Price and Boekelheide (*loc. cit.*) for the synthesis of Chloroquin base, employing the above series of reactions, was without success. It was then considered to be of interest to study the cyclodehydration of β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -carbethoxyacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide to the quinoline derivative, which on subsequent hydrolysis, decarboxylation and demethylation would furnish the desired 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinoline. For this, *p*-anisidine was first allowed to react with malonic ester; the proportion of the desired carbethoxy-acet-*p*-anisidide was reduced due to the formation of the dianilide in spite of the use of a large excess of malonic ester. The amide was then directly condensed with ethyl orthoformate and *m*-chloroaniline to furnish the desired β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -carbethoxyacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide in good yield. But the cyclodehydration of the compound afforded the 3-carbethoxyquinoline derivative in poor yield, which was hydrolysed and decarboxylated to 7-chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilinoquinoline and compared with an authentic sample prepared in an unambiguous way by reacting *p*-anisidine with 4:7-dichloroquinoline. The compound was demethylated with hydrobromic acid to furnish the hydroxy compound, which on the application of the Mannich reaction, using diethylamine, would give camoquin.

When the work was completed, we came across an abstract of a patent in which the above series of reactions using *p*-phenetidine instead of *p*-anisidine have been described (Indian Patent 46,767; *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 10557^o)

EXPERIMENTAL

Carbethoxyaceto-p-anisidide.—A mixture of *p*-anisidine (30 g.) and malonic ester (100 g.) in a Claisen flask was quickly heated in an oil-bath to 150°. Soon the reaction set in and the alcohol began to distill over. As the reaction slowed down, the temperature was gradually raised to 175° and maintained thereabout until no further amount of alcohol distilled over. Based on the amount of *p*-anisidine used, theoretical amount of alcohol was collected. Excess of malonic ester was then removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol (*ca.* 200 c.c.) and filtered hot. The dianilide, which separated on cooling, was filtered off and was washed with a small amount of alcohol. The dianilide on crystallisation from a large volume of alcohol melted at 226-28°. The filtrate was clarified with charcoal and the solvent distilled off. The residue was then refluxed with petroleum ether (60-80°), cooled and the separated solid (30 g.) was collected, m.p. 68-70°. On recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether, the colorless needles melted at 70-72°. (Found: N, 5.65. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4N$ requires N, 5.90%).

*β -m-Chloroanilino- α -carbethoxyacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide*.—A mixture of carbethoxy-*p*-anisidide (32 g.), ethyl orthoformate (20 g.) and *m*-chloroaniline (19.2 g.) in a Claisen flask was slowly heated in an oil-bath to 180°, when theoretical amount of alcohol slowly distilled over. After cooling, the reaction mixture was dissolved in minimum amount of rectified spirit and filtered hot. The crystalline product obtained was collected and was twice recrystallised from the same solvent, m.p. 114°, yield 14 g. (Found: N, 6.99. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 7.42%).

7-Chloro-3-carbethoxy-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilinoquinoline.—To a solution of 33.7 g. of acrylate in 200 c.c. of dry thiophene-free benzene, 17.5 c.c. of POCl_3 was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 hours. After the reaction was over, benzene and the excess of POCl_3 were distilled off under reduced pressure. The residual viscous mass solidified on cooling. This was then warmed with aqueous potassium carbonate. The pasty mass was crystallised twice from alcohol to yield almost colorless needles, m.p. $132-34^\circ$, yield 6 g. (Found: N, 7.38. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 7.85%).

7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilino-3-quinoline Carboxylic Acid.—Ethyl 7-chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilino-3-quinoline carboxylate was dissolved in 30 c.c. of 25% methanolic KOH solution and was allowed to stand at room temperature for 6 hours. During the period the mixture was found to solidify *en masse*. Methyl alcohol was then removed under water pump and the residue dissolved in water, filtered and acidified. The precipitated quinoline carboxylic acid was collected, washed thoroughly and dried (m.p. $278-280^\circ$). This was not characterised but proceeded with the next step.

7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilinoquinoline.—(a). The above acid (2 g.) was heated in a test tube in a bath maintained at $280-90^\circ$. After the evolution of CO_2 had ceased, the tube was cooled, powdered and extracted with boiling alcohol. On concentration, a crystalline solid separated which on one recrystallisation melted at $206-207^\circ$; undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample, m.p. $210-11^\circ$, prepared by the method (b).

(b). To a solution of *p*-anisidine (6.15 g.) in 50 c.c. of normal hydrochloric acid 4:7-dichloroquinoline (9.9 g.) was added and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours, kept overnight and filtered. The solid was then stirred with an excess of concentrated solution of ammonia, filtered, washed thoroughly and dried (yield 95%); this was then recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. $210-11^\circ$. (Found: N, 9.72. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 9.81%).

7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinoline.—A sample of 7-chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)-anilinoquinoline (6 g.) was treated with 60 c.c. of constant boiling hydrobromic acid and the mixture was heated under reflux for 8 hours, cooled, filtered in a sintered glass funnel and washed with a small quantity of water. The quinoline hydrobromide was then stirred with an excess of concentrated solution of ammonia, filtered, washed thoroughly and dried (yield 80%) and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. $256-58^\circ$. The mixed melting point determination with a sample prepared by the method of Burckhalter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1024) recorded no depression.